

Revisiting the Maintenance and Abuse of Human Rights in International Politics: A Legalistic Approach As Derived From the United Nations Universal Declaration, Adopted and Proclaimed By the General Assembly Resolutions

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Abstract: The position of man on earth is one, recognized even by the law of nature, which ensures survival or revolves around the struggle between survival and its irony. Man by nature is free, in modern political systems under the so called democratic principles and values, man is to live under protection of the law and his fundamental virtues respected in the society. The paper tries to look into the issue of human rights in contemporary global politics. With the help of library instrument, the paper finds out that, democratic and non-democratic states maintain such declarations on human rights, especially the one proclaimed by the UN general assembly, but on the other hand, states also abuse such fundamental rights of man. The paper concludes that, such rights are usually abused as a result of ethnicity, religious differences as well as political and economic reasons. The paper recommends absolute practice of the rule of law, strong retribution against aberration of such fundamental rights of man.

Keywords: human rights; abuse; universal; declaration; international politics; United Nations.

INTRODUCTION

The global politics today is generally defined by the legal framework of fundamental and universal rights of individuals and states. The rights of nation-states are glaringly defined by the international law, the rights and duties of citizens in every state have also been defined by the constitution of the state. But there are some basic rights that are inalienable which are also called universal human rights, meaning that every human being possesses such rights irrespective of where he comes from, what race, religion, gender and history. But it is also clear that these rights in contemporary world system and global politics are subject to aberration and abuse, hence the attempts by legal practitioners all over the world to rise against all odds in fighting the abuse of universal human rights.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The materials used in conducting this research were derived from print materials and internet sources of materialistic instruments. This method is in research, identified as the secondary method of data collection, making use of library materials such as books, journals, periodicals, magazines, news papers and reports. The theoretical framework adopted in this research is the liberalist approach, which presupposes freedom, peace and security of all. With the twilight of the first world war, one of the prominent

proponents of liberalism (idealism) was Woodrow Wilson of the united states, who adopted the instrument of the rights to freedom, peace and security all over the world, and worked for an organizational framework (the league of nations/ united nations) to enforce these rights. One basic argument which backs up the liberalist school is that, when such rights to freedom, peace and security are respected, nations will not fight among themselves, world economy will develop and there will be social solidarity and cohesion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Freedom and Equality

While considering the United Nations universal declaration on human rights, it has been established that:

All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood... Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the

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basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it is independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty (UNDHR, 1948).

The issue of human beings being born free presupposes economic, social, political and cultural freedom. But men in their states are not free based on the items mentioned above. One can not argue that in a global capitalist system, men and women are the same. People are not equal even in dignity and the rights they are supposed to enjoy. This is also manifest not only in societies where dictatorship is pronounced, but even in the so called advanced or developed nations. In the United States, there is this issue of racism, discrimination and the feeling that the whites are superior in terms of dignity and other essential services provided by the state for the citizens to enjoy.

Security and Slavery

The united nations universal declaration on human rights has clearly stated the freedom of man to life, security and be free from all sorts of enslavement. But the case in world today is quiet contrary to these provisions. People die innocently as a result of the

absence of security. Insecurity some times arises as a result of economic problems, war and conquest. People that are hungry may create havoc and violence that may lead to the death of many. In terms of wars caused by selfish interest of politicians and state actors, people loose their lives as a result of such selfish interest. The United Nations believes that:

Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person...No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms...No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment...All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. ...All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination (UNDHR, 1948).

The global awareness on international law as well as the universal human rights has virtually increased, but the increment goes hand in hand with an increase in the violation of these rights. The table below shows how slavery, child trafficking and labor has been on the increase in the contemporary world system.

Global Slavery and Child Trafficking

<p>Enslavement: 27 million – Number of people in modern-day slavery across the world. According to the U.S. Department of State’s 2007 Trafficking in Persons Report (TIP Report), estimates vary from 4 to 27 million. The International Labor Organization (ILO) estimates 2.4 million people were victims of human trafficking from 1995-2005. This estimate uses the UN Protocol definition of human trafficking, and includes both transnational and internal data. 800,000 – Number of people trafficked across international borders every year.</p>
<p>Child Slavery and Trafficking: 1 million – Number of children exploited by the global commercial sex trade, every year. 50% Percent of transnational victims who are children. 80% Percent of transnational victims who are women and girls. 70% Percent of female victims who are trafficked into the commercial sex industry. This means that 30% of female victims are victims of forced labor.</p>
<p>Victim, Origin, Transit and Destination Countries: 161 – Countries identified as affected by human trafficking: 127 countries of origin; 98 transit countries; 137 destination countries.</p>
<p>Share of Industrialized Countries: 32 billion – Total yearly profits generated by the human trafficking industry. \$15.5 billion is made in industrialized countries. \$9.7 billion in Asia. \$13,000 per year generated on average by each “forced laborer.” This number can be as high as \$67,200 per victim per year.</p>
<p>The Victims: The majority of trafficking victims are between 18 and 24 years of age. An estimated 1.2 million children are trafficked each year. 95% of victims experienced physical or sexual violence during trafficking (based on data from selected European countries). 43% of victims are used for forced commercial sexual exploitation, of which 98 per cent are women and girls. 32% of victims are used for forced economic exploitation, of which 56 per cent are women and girls. Many trafficking victims have at least middle-level education.</p>
<p>The Traffickers: 52% of those recruiting victims are men, 42% are women and 6% are both men and women. In 54% of cases the recruiter was a stranger to the victim, 46% of cases the recruiter was known to victim. The majority of suspects involved in the trafficking process are nationals of the country where the trafficking process is occurring.</p>
<p>The Profits: Estimated global annual profits made from the exploitation of all trafficked forced labour are US\$ 31.6 billion. Of this: US\$ 15.5 billion – 49% – is generated in industrialized economies. US\$ 9.7 billion – 30.6% is generated in Asia and the Pacific. US\$ 1.3 billion – 4.1% is generated in Latin America and the Caribbean. US\$ 1.6 billion – 5% is generated in sub-Saharan Africa. US\$ 1.5 billion – 4.7% is generated in the Middle East and North</p>

Africa.

Prosecutions: In 2006 there were only 5,808 prosecutions and 3,160 convictions throughout the world. This means that for every 800 people trafficked, only one person was convicted in 2006. Today, every country has a law against slavery. Between 14,000 and 17,500 people are trafficked into the US annually. In 1850, the cost of a slave (in today's dollars) was \$40,000. In modern slavery, the price of a slave is \$30,000 to \$80,000. 600,000 to 800,000 people are trafficked across national borders each year. According to the United Nations, profits from human trafficking rank it among the top three revenue earners for organized crime, after drugs and arms.

Source: U.S. Department of Justice, *Assessment of U.S. Government Activities to Combat Trafficking in Persons: 2004*; ILO, *A global alliance against forced labor: 2005*; UN Office on Drugs and Crime, *Trafficking in Persons: Global Patterns: April 2006*.

The table above has seen the nature of abuse of human rights in the area of slavery, child labor and trafficking in women and children. Albeit, the international community is trying to curtail this trend, but in the third world societies, the menace is escalating, and the developed countries are destinations. More efforts must be put in place in curbing the problem of trafficking and slavery. Some countries are really fighting slavery, child labor and child sex, while some are not doing much to fight the trend. It is against this backdrop that Olga (2013) wrote:

China, Russia, and Uzbekistan have been named among the worst offenders when it comes to human trafficking, according to a State Department report released Wednesday, joining Iran, North Korea, Cuba, Sudan, and Zimbabwe on the bottom "tier" of the U.S. human trafficking rank. Their lower designation means the U.S. may sanction those countries with measures like cancelling non-humanitarian and military assistance, ending exchange visits for government officials, and voting against any IMF or World Bank loans.

The Right to Religious Belief

The United Nations has recognized people with religious belief to be free from any form of discrimination, persecution or marginalization. The universal declaration says:

Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in teaching, practice, worship and observance (UNDHR, 1948).

This right has been globally violated when we consider the level of existence of other religions especially in the United States and Europe, the existence of other religions in Asia and the Middle East. Religion as a belief system flourishes all over the world through all civilizations and empires. The prophets of God who preached for the total submission to the will of God lived among people with different religious belief. Any move or attempt to deny people of their right to religious belief is therefore violating the United Nations universal declaration on human right.

The Extermination of the Rohingya Muslims

It was in 2005 that the pro military government's Mogh intellectual Aye Chan's co-authored book "Influx Viruse" demeaning Rohingyas as deadly enemies needed to be exterminated.

2006 The anti-Muslim riot from a rumor that some Muslim men raped a Burmese woman supported by some Buddhist Monks and opposed by other peace-loving Burmese in Rangoon but spread to Arakan causing tension between the Muslims and the Buddhists. The ban on Rohingyas getting married to Rohingyas introduced a genocidal crime against humanity.

In 2006 the ANC (Arakani National Council) a xenophobic Mogh organization declares the Rohingyas as Bangladeshis and in the agenda recommends to the democracy leaders to exclude Rohingyas from any future share of power in Arakan. In the same year 2006, Aung San Su Ki, the elected democracy movement leader continues to remain under house arrest in Burma away from her family for years.

Still in 2006, Burmese democracy movement continues at home and abroad. However, primarily due to Rohingya's racial differences with the Burmans, secondly, due to the existence of some xenophobic but powerful Mogh leaders now leading the democracy movement in the Arakan province, the Rohingyas issue of statelessness remains largely an unpopular topic among Burma's high level democracy leaders.

According to the Constitution, those ethnic groups that lived within the Burmese territory before 1823 are the natives of Burma and are qualified to be the citizens of Burma. Rohingyas are not included in this definition and branded as foreigners in Burma. Burma has one hundred and thirty five recognized ethnic groups but Rohingyas are not included among them.

in 2009, There was a report of an increased number of Rohingya boat people in the sea: "With the refugee camps in Bangladesh long having stopped taking people, the Rohingya are now seeking to travel to Thailand and then make their way overland to Malaysia, and Indonesia. The Thai military has been accused of seizing hundreds of refugees, towing them out to sea and "leaving them to die" without engines and barely any food or water."

2011 March - Thein Sein is sworn in as president of a new, nominally civilian government.

2012 May the alleged rape and murder of a 27-year-old Buddhist Rakhine woman and the murder of 10 Muslim pilgrims triggered deadly sectarian clashes between Buddhist and Muslims in Arakan State starting on 8 June. Leading provocateur working with security forces identified are Aye Chan, Ko Ko Gui.

"According to the regime, as of 12 June, 21 people had died and 1,662 houses and a mosque had been destroyed as a result of the unrest. However, various organizations said that the death toll might be much higher as a result of escalating attacks and reprisals affecting Muslim Rohingya and Buddhist Rakhine.

"The authorities' decades-long discriminatory policies and practices targeting Rohingya have reinforced the racial and religious animosity between the two communities in Arakan State. Rohingya have suffered restrictions on marriage, freedom of movement, and religious practice. In addition, the regime has routinely subjected Rohingya to forced labor, extortion, land confiscation, and other human rights abuses.

2012 June - Communal violence breaks out between Rakhine Buddhists and the Muslim Rohingya minority in Rakhine State. President Sein declares a state of emergency. Over 2,000 buildings, including seven mosques and nine Buddhist monasteries, have been destroyed. 90,000 people have been displaced. Bangladesh pushes back more than 2,000 Rohingya fleeing violence in Arakan State. Bangladeshi FM says Bangladesh cannot take any more refugees from Burma "under any circumstances."

2012 July, Thein Sein "told the United Nations that the million Rohingya people in Rakhine (formerly known as Arakhan) state are simply not welcome in Myanmar. They would be placed in camps or, preferably, deported. They are ethnically different from the Burman majority, and they are religiously Muslim, he said. The only solution is to hand them over to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees or resettle them in third countries that are willing to take them."

The Bangkok Post Editorial said: "President Thein Sein uttered some of the most distressing statements heard from a reform government in recent memory," "the country and its leader still have a long way to travel to catch up on its 48 years as a cruel, violent military dictatorship. "Myanmar is emerging from a long, dark history of violence. It is entering a new world, with norms that are quite different from 50 years ago. Thein Sein's statements about the Rohingya appear racist, malicious and threatening. They must not stand unchallenged."

The recent ethnic clashes in western Myanmar have thrown off the facade of Burma of the past. International protest by foreign governments and NGOs protests against Burmese government's hostile state policy. The reports coming from Arakan confirms that the ethnic cleansing of the Rohingya people continues.

Source: Burma: A Country Study. March 1983. Edited by Frederica M. Bunge. Washington, D.C.: Department of the Army; Human Rights Watch (HRW)/Asia. 7 May 1992.

People of any religious belief must not be hated. There is freedom of religion every where in the world and this right must be respected. The United Nations must impose sanctions on any nation, people or

leaders who abuse this international right of the people. Carnage of the Muslims was reported in the Central African Republic, religious intolerance in Myanmar against the Rohingyas, and many other

places against the Christians. This right must be monitored and respected before a stable democracy is put in place.

Freedom to Hold an Opinion and To Expression

The essence of the media under mass communication is to provide political, economic, social and cultural socialization; educate, inform and create awareness among people of the political environment. Albeit some people manipulate the media, especially the international and states media, but there should be right for individuals whatsoever and however to express their opinion and feeling about the political, economic and socio-cultural aspects of their life. The United Nations stipulate that:

Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers (UNDHR, 1948).

But in our contemporary world politics, what is obtainable is personalization of the media itself, as the CNN is controlled by the American government; the BBC controlled by the British government; the CCTV news controlled by the communist party of china, in Nigeria for example, the NTA, radio Nigeria and the private radio and TV stations are under the supervision of the government.

Participation and Democracy

Political participation envisages the direct or indirect involvement of the citizenry in the process of leadership or governance of the society. Participation is direct when the citizens physically participate, it is also indirect when representatives are chosen by the citizens to make, execute and interpret the laws on behalf of them. From the UN submission under the universal declaration is that:

Everyone has the right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through freely chosen representatives. Everyone has the right of equal access to public service in his country. The will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of government; this will, shall be expressed in periodic and genuine elections which shall be by universal and equal suffrage and shall be held by secret vote or by equivalent free voting procedures (UNDHR, 1948).

From the above declaration, it can be understood that, periodic elections are not usually held in many states in the world today, for nations are still practicing monarchical system and some are dictators. The important point to note here is that, periodic elections

should also be free and fair, but what is seen in the global system today is self succession and perpetuation. It is also in line with this argument that Larry (2002) argues:

The last quarter of the twentieth century witnessed the greatest expansion of democracy in the history of the world. If we define democracy in the minimal sense, as a system of government in which the principal positions of political power are filled through regular, free, and fair elections, then about three of every five independent states in the world are democracies today. In the judgment of Freedom House, there were 121 democracies in the world at the end of 2001—the highest number in history. Some of these regimes, possibly as many as seventeen, may be better classified as “competitive authoritarian,” in the sense that elections, while competitive, are either not free and fair or do not confer on those elected full power to rule.

Political participation and democratic values have continued to flourish all over the world as a result of western pontification of the concept of democracy and the perpetual polarization of the world society as democratic states and axis of evil. But it is not ideal to accept quantity than quality because the quality of democracies today, is questionable. It is this questionable status of democracies that Larry diamond asks:

Beyond the leveling off of democratic expansion since the mid-1990s, there have been four other major caveats to the democratizing trend. First, the quality of governance and the rule of law have actually deteriorated in some existing democracies, and the more recently established democracies have tended to be less liberal and more corrupt. Second, the spread of democracy has been far from uniform across regions and sub-regions. While some regions of the world are now overwhelmingly democratic, others have been only very partially touched by the democratic trend, while the Arab world remains without a single true democracy. Third, many regimes particularly in Africa and the former Soviet Union that once appeared to be “in transition” from authoritarian rule have settled into varying shades and forms of authoritarian rule that fall well short of democracy. Finally, many of the democracies that have come into being in the past two decades exhibit growing problems of governance that are eroding their legitimacy among the public and undermining their stability (UNDHR, 1948).

Most countries in world system today only claim to be democratic but by its veritable tenets they are not democratic. Many states in Africa, Asia Latin America and the Caribbean are quasi-democratic. Some countries in Eastern Europe and central Asia are far away from being democratic despite the fact that they conduct elections. Such elections are not free and fair and the process of the electioneering is also undemocratic.

Right to Security

The original contract signed between the citizens and the state when social contract is revisited, is that, the citizens have their duties to perform of being loyal and obedient to the state, where by on the other hand, the state has to provide security and social welfare to the citizens. The UN declaration states that:

Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization,

through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality (UNDHR, 1948).

Social security is provided in societies where freedom of individual is respected and seen cherishable. In many societies in the world today, social security does not exist, poverty is the order of the day and survival is for the fittest. Unemployment is prevalent and people are finding ways to be self reliant. As a result of lack of social security, social vices have replaced the societal order. Armed robbery, kidnapping, prostitution and child labor are on the increase and Ethno-religious violence spreading across borders.

Table 1.1 Unemployment around The World, 2003-2012 (% of Labor Force)

Country	ISO	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	Estimates Start After
Albania	ALB	15.0	14.4	14.1	13.8	13.2	12.5	13.6	13.6	13.3	15.0	2011
Algeria	DZA	23.7	17.7	15.3	12.5	13.8	11.3	10.2	10.0	10.0	9.7	2011
Argentina	ARG	17.3	13.6	11.6	10.2	8.5	7.9	8.7	7.8	7.2	7.2	2010
Armenia	ARM	31.2	31.6	31.2	27.8	28.7	16.4	18.7	19.0	19.0	19.0	
Australia	AUS	5.9	5.4	5.1	4.8	4.4	4.3	5.6	5.2	5.1	5.2	2011
Austria	AUT	4.3	4.9	5.2	4.8	4.4	3.8	4.8	4.4	4.2	4.3	2011
Azerbaijan	AZE	9.7	8.4	7.6	6.8	6.5	6.1	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	2009
The Bahamas	BHS	10.8	10.2	10.2	7.6	7.9	8.7	14.2	14.0	13.7	11.0	2009
Barbados	BRB	11.0	9.6	9.7	8.7	7.4	8.1	10.2	10.6	11.5	11.0	2011
Belarus	BLR	3.1	1.9	1.5	1.2	1.0	0.8	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.6	2011
Belgium	BEL	8.2	8.4	8.5	8.3	8.6	7.0	7.9	8.3	7.2	7.4	2011
Belize	BLZ	12.9	11.6	11.0	9.4	12.1	10.8	12.7	11.2	11.4	11.3	2009
Bhutan	BTN		2.5	2.3	3.2	3.7	4.0	4.0	3.3	3.1	3.2	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BIH	31.1	31.1	31.1	31.1	29.0	23.4	24.1	27.2	27.6	27.6	2010
Brazil	BRA	12.3	11.5	9.8	10.0	9.3	7.9	8.1	6.7	6.0	6.0	2011
Brunei Darussalam	BRN	4.5	3.5	4.1	4.0	3.4	3.7	3.5	2.7	2.7	2.7	2010
Bulgaria	BGR	13.9	12.2	10.2	9.0	6.9	5.7	6.9	10.3	11.3	11.5	
Canada	CAN	7.6	7.2	6.8	6.3	6.1	6.2	8.3	8.0	7.5	7.3	2011
Cape Verde	CPV	20.0	19.5	19.0	18.3	17.8	17.0	11.1	10.3	10.0	10.0	2009
Chile	CHL	9.5	10.0	9.3	8.0	7.0	7.8	10.8	8.2	7.1	6.6	2011
China	CHN	4.3	4.2	4.2	4.1	4.0	4.2	4.3	4.1	4.1	4.1	2011

Colombia	COL	14.2	13.6	11.8	12.0	11.2	11.3	12.0	11.8	10.8	11.0	2010
Costa Rica	CRI	6.7	6.5	6.6	6.0	4.6	4.9	7.8	7.3	7.7	7.5	2010
Croatia	HRV	14.3	13.8	12.7	11.1	9.4	8.3	9.1	12.2	13.7	14.2	2011
Cyprus	CYP	4.1	4.7	5.4	4.5	3.9	3.7	5.4	6.2	7.8	11.7	2011
Czech Republic	CZE	7.8	8.3	7.9	7.1	5.3	4.4	6.7	7.3	6.7	7.0	2010
Denmark	DNK	5.4	5.5	4.8	3.9	3.8	3.4	6.1	7.5	6.1	5.6	2011
Dominican Republic	DOM	16.4	17.0	17.9	16.0	15.5	14.2	14.9	14.0	14.6	13.0	2011
Ecuador	ECU	9.8	11.0	10.7	10.1	8.8	6.9	8.5	7.6	6.0	5.8	2011
Egypt	EGY	11.3	10.5	11.5	10.9	9.2	8.7	9.4	9.2	12.1	12.7	2010
El Salvador	SLV	6.9	6.8	7.2	6.6	6.3	5.9	8.1	5.8	5.8	5.5	
Estonia	EST	10.0	9.7	7.9	5.9	4.7	5.5	13.8	17.3	12.5	10.1	2011
Ethiopia	ETH											
Fiji	FJI	8.1	5.8	5.9	6.4	7.5	7.5	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	2007
Finland	FIN	9.0	8.8	8.4	7.7	6.9	6.4	8.2	8.4	7.8	7.6	2011
France	FRA	8.9	9.3	9.3	9.2	8.4	7.8	9.5	9.7	9.6	10.1	2011
Georgia	GEO	11.5	12.6	13.8	13.6	13.3	16.5	16.9	16.3	15.1	14.2	2009
Germany	DEU	9.8	10.5	11.2	10.2	8.8	7.6	7.7	7.1	6.0	5.2	2011
Greece	GRC	9.7	10.5	9.9	8.9	8.3	7.7	9.4	12.5	17.3	23.8	2011
Honduras	HND	5.1	5.9	4.0	3.9	3.9	3.9	4.4	4.6	4.4	4.4	2001
Hong Kong SAR	HKG	7.9	6.8	5.6	4.8	4.0	3.5	5.2	4.3	3.4	3.4	2011
Hungary	HUN	5.5	6.3	7.3	7.5	7.7	8.0	10.1	11.2	11.0	10.9	2011
Iceland	ISL	3.4	3.1	2.1	1.3	1.0	1.6	8.0	8.1	7.4	6.1	2010
Indonesia	IDN	9.5	9.9	11.2	10.3	9.1	8.4	7.9	7.1	6.6	6.2	2011
Islamic Republic of Iran	IRN	11.3	10.3	12.1	12.1	10.5	10.4	11.9	13.5	12.3	14.1	2010
Ireland	IRL	4.6	4.5	4.4	4.4	4.6	6.3	11.8	13.6	14.4	14.8	2011
Israel	ISR	13.4	12.9	11.2	10.5	9.2	7.7	9.4	8.3	7.1	7.0	2011
Italy	ITA	8.5	8.0	7.7	6.8	6.1	6.8	7.8	8.4	8.4	10.6	2011

Jamaica	JAM	11.8	12.2	11.2	10.3	9.9	10.6	11.4	12.4	12.8	13.0	2010
Japan	JPN	5.2	4.7	4.4	4.1	3.8	4.0	5.1	5.0	4.6	4.5	2011
Jordan	JOR	14.4	14.7	14.8	14.1	13.1	12.7	12.9	12.5	12.9	12.9	2011
Kazakhstan	KAZ	8.8	8.4	8.1	7.8	7.3	6.6	6.6	5.8	5.4	5.4	2011
Korea	KOR	3.6	3.7	3.7	3.5	3.3	3.2	3.7	3.7	3.4	3.3	2011
Kuwait	KWT	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.6	2.1	2.1	2.1	2011
Kyrgyz Republic	KGZ	9.9	8.5	8.1	8.3	8.2	8.2	8.4	8.6	7.9	7.7	2010
Latvia	LVA	10.6	10.4	9.0	6.8	6.1	7.5	16.9	18.7	16.2	15.3	2011
Lithuania	LTU	12.4	11.4	8.3	5.6	4.3	5.8	13.7	17.8	15.4	13.5	2011
Luxembourg	LUX	3.5	3.9	4.3	4.5	4.4	4.4	5.8	6.2	5.7	6.2	2011
FYR Macedonia	MKD	36.7	37.2	37.3	36.0	34.9	33.8	32.2	32.1	31.4	31.9	2011
Malaysia	MYS	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.3	3.2	3.3	3.7	3.3	3.1	3.1	2011
Malta	MLT	7.7	7.2	7.3	6.9	6.5	6.1	6.9	7.0	6.5	6.0	2010
Mauritius	MUS	7.7	8.4	9.6	9.1	8.5	7.2	7.3	7.8	7.9	8.1	2011
Mexico	MEX	3.4	3.9	3.6	3.6	3.7	4.0	5.5	5.4	5.2	4.8	2011
Moldova	MDA	7.9	8.1	7.3	7.4	5.1	4.0	6.4	7.4	6.7	5.8	2011
Mongolia	MNG					11.3	9.2	11.6	9.9	7.7	6.8	2011
Morocco	MAR	11.4	10.8	11.1	9.7	9.8	9.6	9.1	9.1	8.9	8.8	2011
Myanmar	MMR	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	2009
Netherlands	NLD	4.2	5.1	5.3	4.4	3.6	3.1	3.7	4.5	4.4	5.2	2011
New Zealand	NZL	4.8	4.1	3.8	3.8	3.7	4.2	6.1	6.5	6.5	6.6	2011
Nicaragua	NIC	11.7	11.0	5.6	5.2	5.9	6.1	8.2	7.8	7.8	7.8	2010
Nigeria	NGA	14.8	13.4	11.9	12.3	12.7	14.9	19.7	21.1	23.9		2011
Norway	NOR	4.5	4.5	4.6	3.4	2.5	2.6	3.2	3.6	3.3	3.1	2011
Pakistan	PAK	8.3	7.7	7.7	6.2	5.3	5.2	5.5	5.6	6.0	7.7	2011
Panama	PAN	13.7	12.4	10.3	9.1	6.8	5.8	5.0	4.5	4.2	4.2	2011
Paraguay	PRY	8.1	7.3	5.8	6.7	5.6	5.7	6.4	5.7	5.6	5.8	2011
Peru	PER	9.4	9.4	9.6	8.5	8.4	8.4	8.4	7.9	7.7	7.5	2011

{ Philippines	PHL	11.4	11.8	11.4	8.0	7.3	7.4	7.5	7.3	7.0	7.0	2011
{ Poland	POL	19.6	19.0	17.7	13.8	9.6	7.1	8.2	9.6	9.6	10.0	2011
{ Portugal	PRT	6.3	6.7	7.6	7.7	8.0	7.6	9.5	10.8	12.7	15.5	2011
{ Romania	ROU	7.0	8.1	7.2	7.3	6.4	5.8	6.9	7.3	7.4	7.2	2010
{ Russia	RUS	8.6	8.2	7.6	7.2	6.1	6.4	8.4	7.5	6.5	6.0	2011
{ San Marino		4.1	3.4	3.6	3.3	3.0	3.1	4.5	4.9	5.5	6.6	2011
{ Sao Tomè and Principe	STP	16.4	16.6	17.3	16.4	16.2	15.9	15.5	15.1	14.7	14.2	2008
{ Saudi Arabia	SAU	10.4	11.0	11.5	12.0	11.0	9.8	10.5	10.0			2010
{ Serbia	SRB	16.0	19.5	21.8	21.6	18.8	14.7	17.4	20.0	24.4	25.6	2011
{ Seychelles	SYC	3.2	3.5	3.6	2.5	1.9	1.7	5.1	4.6	4.1	3.7	2011
{ Singapore	SGP	4.0	3.4	3.1	2.7	2.1	2.2	3.0	2.2	2.0	2.1	2011
{ Slovak Republic	SVK	17.4	18.1	16.2	13.3	11.0	9.6	12.1	14.4	13.5	13.7	2011
{ Slovenia	SVN	6.7	6.3	6.5	6.0	4.9	4.4	5.9	7.3	8.2	8.8	2011
{ South Africa	ZAF	28.0	26.2	26.7	25.5	22.2	22.9	23.9	24.0	23.9	24.4	2010
{ Spain	ESP	11.5	11.0	9.2	8.5	8.3	11.3	18.0	20.1	21.7	24.9	2011
{ Sri Lanka	LKA	8.4	8.3	7.7	6.6	6.2	6.0	5.9	4.9	4.9	4.9	2011
{ Sudan	SDN	15.8	16.2	17.0	17.5	16.8	16.0	14.9	13.7	12.0	10.8	2010
{ Suriname	SUR	7.0	8.0	11.0	12.0	11.0	9.0					2008
{ Sweden	SWE	5.6	6.3	7.6	7.0	6.1	6.2	8.3	8.4	7.5	7.5	2011
{ Switzerland	CHE	3.4	3.5	3.4	2.9	2.4	2.6	3.7	3.5	2.8	3.4	2011
{ Syria	SYR	10.8	12.3	8.0	8.3	9.2	10.9	8.1	8.6			2010
{ Taiwan Province of China	TWN	5.0	4.4	4.1	3.9	3.9	4.1	5.9	5.2	4.4	4.5	2011
{ Thailand	THA	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.0	0.7	0.7	2011
{ Trinidad and Tobago	TTO	10.3	8.3	8.0	6.2	5.6	4.6	5.3	5.9	5.1	5.5	2011
{ Tunisia	TUN	14.5	14.2	12.8	12.5	12.4	12.4	13.3	13.0	18.9	17.0	2011
{ Turkey	TUR	10.5	10.3	10.6	10.2	10.2	10.9	14.0	11.9	9.8	9.4	2011

(Ukraine	UKR	9.1	8.6	7.2	6.8	6.4	6.4	8.8	8.1	7.9	7.8	2011
(United Kingdom	GBR	5.0	4.8	4.8	5.4	5.4	5.6	7.5	7.9	8.0	8.1	2011
(United States	USA	6.0	5.5	5.1	4.6	4.6	5.8	9.3	9.6	9.0	8.2	2011
(Uruguay	URY	17.1	13.3	12.1	10.9	9.2	7.6	7.3	6.7	6.0	6.7	2010
(Uzbekistan	UZB	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	
(Venezuela	VEN	18.1	15.1	12.2	10.0	8.5	7.4	7.9	8.6	8.1	8.0	2011
(Vietnam	VNM	5.8	5.6	5.3	4.8	4.6	4.7	4.6	4.3	4.5	4.5	2010

Source: <http://www.gfmag.com/component/content/article/119-economic-data/12384-worlds-unemployment-ratescom.html#ixzz2gm4SrSEY>

Right to Education

Every child has the right to education in the global system. A parent who refuses the education of his child is violating the universal declaration. The United Nations states that:

Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit. Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace. Parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children (UNDHR, 1948).

The basic fact about education in the world today is that, the rich goes to school while the poor remains out of school. In the United States for example, the blacks remain out of school and venture into music, drugs and prostitution, while the whites obtain the best qualifications in the states. In Africa, Asia and other continents, it is apparent that education is becoming expensive for an ordinary man, and many

children drop out of school for the failure of their parents to pay their tuition fees.

The concept of illiteracy as conceived and defined by the United Nations encompasses inability to read and write. The level has dropped significantly since in the 1950's, but the prediction made on illiteracy all over the world, is that it will increase especially in the twenty-first century.

The United Nations sees illiteracy as the inability to read and write a simple message in any language. In the first survey (1950) at least 44% of the world's population was found to be illiterate. A 1978 study showed the rate to have dropped to 32.5%, by 1990 illiteracy worldwide had dropped to about 27%, and by 1998 to 16%. However, a study by the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) published in 1998 predicted that the world illiteracy rate would increase in the 21st century, because only a quarter of the world's children were in school by the end of the 20th century. The highest illiteracy rates were found in the less developed nations of Africa, Asia, and South America; the lowest in Australia, Japan, North Korea, and the more technologically advanced nations of Europe and North America. Using the UN definition of illiteracy, the United States and Canada have an overall illiteracy rate of about 1%. In certain disadvantaged areas, however, such as the rural South in the United States, the illiteracy rate is much higher (CEE, 2012).

Education therefore, is a right of all not a privilege. But the elite class in developing countries of Africa, Asia, the Middle East and the Caribbean has developed a culture of sending their children to private and foreign schools, while the poor still continue to attend public schools which teachers are underpaid and no adequate resources and good atmosphere of learning put in place.

CONCLUSION

The failure of governments and state actors to respect human rights in international politics is highly attached to ethnic rivalry, religious differences, political and economic reasons. Ethnicity is a driving force for conflict conflicts around the world-this is seeable in the Bosnian crisis, were the rights of other people to education, to religion and even to live were abused by the ethnic Serbs. Politics is a process which involves acquiring political power through a struggle. Fear of elimination in the process, results in the abuse of human rights. Capitalism is a strong economic factor for the abuse of human rights in many cases and places in the world today. Capitalism is all about maximization of profit even if in the process others might be hurt.

RECOMMENDATION

Some of the recommended ways through which the issue of the abuse of human rights can be contained, can be seen as follows:

Rule of law all over the world must be respected and adhered to in any form of socio-economic and political formation.

Any form of impunity on human right abuse should be investigated by a special institution and be seriously dealt with.

The United Nations should also consolidate its effort towards dealing with political actors who strongly abuse fundamental rights of their people.

In case of tribal, ethnic or religious conflicts, the perpetrators must be prosecuted, and an appropriate action or judicial action be delivered to serve as a lesson for others.

Corrupt leaders all over the world must be asked to step down in the case of gross misconduct and misappropriation of public funds all over the world.

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